

A speech therapist should be able to recognize speech disorders, master the techniques and methods of their elimination and correction, special methods of teaching children with speech disorders to their native language both in preschool and school age, carry out preventive work on prevention, know well the psychological characteristics of children with speech pathology, use the techniques and methods of their education, correction and development of higher cortical functions.

The importance of speech therapy is important for all speech pathologists, since speech disorders are much more common in abnormal children than in normal developing children. The most urgent problems of modern speech therapy are the following:

1. Unification of the categorical apparatus.
2. In-depth study (including psycholinguistic) of the mechanisms and methods of correction of speech disorders.
3. Scientifically based correlation of nosological (clinical-pedagogical) and symptomological (psychological-pedagogical) approaches in speech therapy theory and practice and in the development of nomenclature documents.
4. Study of speech ontogenesis in various forms of speech disorders.
5. Study of the features of speech disorders and their elimination in complicated developmental defects.
6. Early prevention, detection and elimination of speech disorders.
7. Creative and scientifically-based development of the content, methods of teaching and upbringing of children with severe speech disorders in special kindergartens and schools.

8. Consistent implementation of a comprehensive approach to the identification and correction of speech disorders.

9. Ensuring continuity in the speech therapy work of preschool, school and medical institutions.

10. Improving the theory and practice of differential diagnosis of various forms of speech disorders. 11. Development of TSO, laboratory and experimental equipment, introduction of computer technology in the educational process.

12. Analysis of achievements in the field of speech therapy, available in domestic and foreign theory and practice.

Speech is a complex function, and its development depends on many points. An important role here is played by the influence of others – the child learns to speak on the example of the speech of parents, teachers, and friends. Others should help the child to form a correct, clear speech. It is very important that the child from an early age hears the correct speech, clearly sounding, on the example of which his own speech is formed.

Speech disorders in one way or another negatively affect the entire mental development of the child, affect his activities and behavior. Severe speech disorders can affect mental development, especially the formation of higher levels of cognitive activity, due to the close relationship between speech and thought.

Statistics of speech disorders invariably record the growth of speech pathologies. Speech disorders are not only manifested in the shortcomings of sound pronunciation, but also affect other components of speech, such as the phonetic, lexical and grammatical side of

speech. The defects are systemic in nature. Children with speech disorders, of course, need the qualified help of a specialist. Many parents are unaware of the severity of the problem, believing that their child is all right. Parents can not independently determine the content of the work on the development of the child and the correction of his shortcomings in the conditions of family education. But the speech therapist not only "puts sounds" : the work of the speech therapist begins with the development of all mental processes in children (visual and auditory perception, attention, memory, thinking), which certainly contributes to the development of the child and his cognitive activity.

Deviations in speech development are of a different nature and are differently associated with the overall development of the child and his cognitive activity, but the lag in learning is inevitable if the child is not provided with speech therapy in a timely manner. But preschool education is the first stage of continuing education.

A possible cause of speech problems is the weakening of the somatic health of children: lagging in physical development, poor nutrition, severe diseases at an early age, more than 4 episodes of acute upper respiratory tract infections in the first year of a child's life{17}

Social factors have a significant impact on the correct formation of the child's speech behavior{12,18}. The mother's speech for the child is the main source about the basics of the native language{12}. In children whose mothers actively talk to them in the first and second year of life(at the stage of speech formation), there are no delays in speech development or the lag is insignificant, and

by the age of three, such children are aligned in development with their peers.

Fine motor skills-The development of fine motor skills is very important for the development of speech in a child. The whole secret is that the area of the cerebral cortex that is responsible for the subtle movements of the fingers is located very close to the speech zone. Accordingly, the more developed the part of the brain responsible for fine motor skills, the greater the impact it has on the speech zone. Fine motor skills improve the smoothness of finger movements, which is very important for further learning to write and the formation of a beautiful handwriting. Thanks to the developed fine motor skills, it is easier for the child to master such household skills as tying shoelaces, eating with the help of cutlery, developed fine motor skills make the child more independent in everyday life.

The connection between mental abilities, speech and fine motor skills of the hand has long been known. In preschool children, this is most pronounced. The movements of the child's fingers and hands have a special developmental effect. Russian physiologists also confirm the connection between brain development and the development of fine motor skills of the hand. Simple hand movements help to remove tension not only from the hands themselves, but also from the lips, relieve mental fatigue. The development of fine motor skills of the hands is very important for the psychophysical development and speech development of the child. Currently, researchers have proven that the development of fine motor skills of the fingers has a positive effect on the formation of children's speech.

The outstanding scientist I. P. Pavlov attached great importance to tactile sensations, proving that they form the speech center. The more perfect the cortex, the more perfect the speech, and therefore the thinking.

The training of fine finger movements will not only have a stimulating effect on the overall development of the child, but will also help to overcome and prevent speech disorders in children. Even if the child's speech develops without features, it is necessary to take care of improving his fine movements of the fingers; if the development of the baby's speech lags behind, special attention should be paid to the training of his fingers.

Therefore, the training of fingers, that is, the development of fine motor skills, should be started as early as possible, especially in children with general speech underdevelopment. Fine motor skills of the hands are developed:

1. Finger gymnastics using poems, songs, nursery rhymes and folk tales.
2. Massage with finger rubbing and hand massagers
3. Folk games with palms
4. Games with natural materials
5. Games with household items
6. Sand and water games
7. Finger Theater
8. Nitrotherapy
9. Ganutel
10. Didactic games

Currently, the problems of studying, diagnosing and correcting writing disorders in children are one of the most urgent tasks of pedagogy and speech therapy. The problem of violations of written speech in schoolchildren is one of the most relevant for school education. About 40% of children from the total

number of primary school students have some type of writing disorder (dysgraphia). Therefore, the problem of helping children with writing disorders remains acute. In this regard, the purpose of this article is to provide a comprehensive analysis of the main violations of writing in primary school children. So, the process of mastering written speech is in close interaction with the degree of formation of all aspects of oral speech: sound pronunciation, phonemic perception, lexico – grammatical side of speech, coherent speech. It follows that the cause of dysgraphia can be the same functional and organic disorders that cause oral speech disorders.

It follows that the cause of dysgraphia can be the same functional and organic disorders that cause oral speech disorders. The key to successful mastery of writing is a sufficiently high level of oral speech development. But it is worth noting that, in contrast to oral speech, written speech can only develop under the condition of systematic and purposeful training{1, p. 7}.

The main sign of dysgraphia is typical and repeated errors of a persistent nature in writing, not related to ignorance of the rules and norms of the language. Such errors include: mixing and replacing graphically similar handwritten letters (sh-sh, t-sh, v-d, m-l) or phonetically similar sounds (b-p, d-t, z-s, g-k); distortion of the letter-syllabic structure of the word (omissions, permutations, addition of letters and syllables); violation of the unity and separation of writing words; agrammatism in writing (violation of inflection and agreement of words in a sentence). Children with dysgraphia have a low speed of writing, difficult to distinguish handwriting, fluctuations in the height and

inclination of letters, slipping off the line. The presence of dysgraphia is diagnosed at the age of 8-9 years {4, p. 131}.

Conclusion: Almost all personal qualities: tastes, habits, character, temperament are laid down in a person in childhood. And speech plays a significant role in the formation of a person. Speech is a complex function, and its development depends on many points. An important role here is played by the influence of others – the child learns to speak on the example of the speech of parents, teachers, and friends. Others should help the child in the formation of a correct clear speech. It is very important that the child from an early age hears the correct speech, clearly sounding, on the example of which his own speech is formed. If a child has speech defects, he is often subjected to ridicule from his peers, offensive remarks, and does not participate in concerts and children's holidays. The child is offended, he does not feel equal among other children. Gradually,

such a child moves away from the team, closes in on himself. He tries to keep silent or answer in monosyllables, not to take part in speech games. The task of the speech therapist, together with the parents, is to convince the child that speech can be corrected, you can help the baby become like everyone else. It is important to interest the child so that he himself wants to participate in the process of speech correction. And for this, classes should not be boring lessons, but an interesting game. The role of speech expressiveness is extremely important. Just do not forget that fine motor skills also play an important role in the development of the child. First of all, it provides the design of phrases, and at the same time, it provides the transmission of information about the communicative type of utterance, about the emotional state of the speaker. It is the preschool age that is most favorable for solving correctional tasks, for mastering the intonation characteristics of speech {6}

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